

METHODOLOGY AND THEORY OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Annotatsiya. *ushbu maqolada chet tillarini oson o'rganish, jahon amaliyoti va muhim nazariyalardan foydalangan holda zamonaviy texnologiyalar yordamida talabalarning o'qish faolligini oshirish va eng muhimi, talaba e'tiborini jalb qila oladigan fan o'quvchisi. o'qituvchining turli usullari va salohiyati muhokama qilinadi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *pedagogic texnologiyalar, metodologiya, usulning asosiy tamoyillari, an'anaviy usul, didaktika, yozma nutq va grammatika.*

Аннотация. *В этой статье рассматривается помощь современных технологий для легкого изучения иностранных языков, использующих мировую практику и важные теории, для повышения активности студентов в учебе и, самое главное, научного читателя, который может привлечь внимание студента. обсуждаются различные методы и потенциал преподавателя.*

Ключевые слова: *педагогические технологии, методология, основные принципы метода, традиционный метод, дидактика, письменная речь и грамматика.*

Abstract. *In this article, the help of modern technologies for easy learning of foreign languages, using world practice and important theories, to increase the activity of students to study and most importantly, a science reader that can attract the attention of the student. different methods and potential of the teacher are discussed.*

Keywords: *Pedagogical technologies, methodology, basic principles of the method, traditional method, didactics, written speech and grammar.*

Introduction.

As we know, today learning and teaching foreign languages arouses a number of positive interests among representatives of various fields. And this necessarily requires them to work together, that is, in cooperation. In world practice, modern pedagogical technologies are gaining importance in the development of students' professional skills in foreign languages. In order to take a worthy place in the world community, it is very important for us to know foreign languages perfectly. In addition, it is important to use advanced pedagogical technologies to learn foreign languages quickly and easily.

The improvement and change in the quality of education mainly depends on the ability of teachers and students to communicate openly and freely during the lesson. The methods and technologies used in the course of the lesson increase the activity of the students during the whole lesson. Pedagogical technologies help students acquire new knowledge, develop a number of necessary skills, and increase students' creative abilities. Pupils receiving education on the basis of new educational principles will help to form well-rounded, educated and spiritually mature people.

Methodology also has a particularly important role in learning foreign languages. Methodology teaches how a teacher should conduct a lesson. Studying the literature on methodological history shows that some researchers call methodology an art. For example, the French methodist Penlash expressed the opinion that there are no “good” or “bad” methods, but

there are “good” or “bad” teachers. In 1924, E. Otto responded to such thoughts with his own thoughts. That is, he said: “If someone considers methodology to be an art, he confuses the theory of science with its practical application.” Each discipline has its own set of concepts.

Foreign language teaching methodology is understood as a set of activities of the teacher and the student. This set includes: practical, educational goals of teaching foreign languages, which contribute to its development. The term method means “the term of educational methods” and “the direction of education”. There are several methods of teaching foreign languages. These are: translation method, correct method, conscious-comparative method, traditional method, intensive method, etc. The methodology of teaching foreign languages is interrelated with didactics, and also the theories of teaching all subjects are based on didactics. Didactics is considered a general theory of education, and methodology is considered as a science of teaching a certain educational subject. The science of teaching a specific language is called lingvomethodology. The term “Method” is associated with the meaning of acquiring knowledge, competence, skills, forming a worldview in students and creating an opportunity to acquire knowledge. It also means the work method of the pedagogue and the student. The application of methods in teaching foreign languages began long ago. Principles are a newer methodological term compared to methods. Historically, the methods were grouped into 4 groups and were called “correct”, “comparative”, “translation” and “mixed”.

Famous Methodist Prof. I. V. Rakhmanov studied the history of methods in depth. The translation method mainly consists of 2 parts, while the foreign language is studied for general educational purposes from the point of view of the grammar-translation method, grammatical exercises are performed in order to improve the logical thinking of the person who wants to learn the language. Grammatical knowledge is accepted as the main goal of education.

Nowadays, the expression of intercultural communication is widely used in the methodology of teaching foreign languages. Intercultural dialogue is a dialogue between representatives of different cultures about their social origin, national character, mentality, lifestyle, traditions and values.

Conclusion.

People experience various complex psychological changes during foreign language learning, which undoubtedly means that foreign language learning is a multifaceted discipline. In particular, there is a comparison between the mother tongue and the foreign language. In overcoming this process, the use of various methods and modern pedagogical technologies is effective. Learning foreign languages in itself means learning knowledge related to its methodology. Different methods of methodology are used in the organization of the lesson process. These methods are: the method of communicative didactics, the method of organizing intercultural communication and the method of organizing exercises. All three methods are closely related and complement each other. As the science of methodology is connected with the science of didactics, the method of communicative didactics is based on communicativeness during learning a foreign language.

In the process of using the method of communicative didactics, the method of formation of intercultural dialogue of pedagogues and teachers is formed. In order to organize the foreign language learning process with a communicative approach and bring it to the level of intercultural communication, it is important to pay attention to the “exercise technology” as the last step. In order to achieve great results in teaching foreign languages, it is necessary to acquire knowledge within the framework of modern pedagogical information and communication technologies.

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